

**Harnessing the Power of Digital Technologies to
Protect Plants & the Environment**

D6.2: Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan

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Executive Summary

This document provides the STELLA Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan. Building upon the initial strategy outlined in the Grant Agreement, this plan details how the project will effectively communicate its findings on early pest detection, warning and response to its target groups.

The underlying principles of the DEC strategy are presented, followed by a thorough description of the actions and tools that will be utilised to effectively share information within the consortium and to transfer project knowledge and results to the targeted stakeholders over the four years of the project lifespan and at least four years beyond its completion.

The key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be used to measure the performance of the DEC plan are clearly defined, along with the planning and reporting procedures all partners will need to apply.

An exploitation strategy describing the exploitable assets, the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management tools and the sustainability approach will be briefly described. This is the first iteration of the DEC plan which will be updated on M18, M32 & M48 to reflect the project's advancements and monitor the plan's implementation.

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms			
AI	Artificial Intelligence	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
D&C	Dissemination & Communication	MAA	Multi Actor Approach
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication	MS	Milestone
DMP	Data Management Plan	NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
EC	European Commission	PLRV	Potato Leafroll Virus
EI	Expected Impact	PSS	Pest Surveillance System
EO	Expected Outcome	R&D	Research and Development
ER	Expected Result	RNQP	Regulated Non-Quarantine Pest
EU	European Union	RPAS	Remotely Piloted Aerial Systems
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation	SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
GIS	Geographic Information System	SOTA	State of the Art
GLV	Grapevine Leafroll Disease	TG	Target Groups
HE	Horizon Europe	UCP	Use Case Pilots
IoT	Internet of Things	VM	Verification Means
IP	Intellectual Property	WP	Work Package
IPM	Integrated Pest Management		

1. Introduction

1.1 Project Summary

STELLA aims to develop a holistic digital system (STELLA PSS) to aid in the early warning and detection of quarantine and regulated plant pathogens, together with a response strategy that uses modern sensing technology and Artificial Intelligence.

The STELLA PSS will undergo a rigorous three-year testing phase across various scales: field, farm, and regional. This evaluation encompasses six Use Case Pilots (UCPs) with diverse characteristics, as detailed in Figure 1. These UCPs include arable land, orchards, vineyards, and even large, geographically challenging areas like forests. The project tackles eight specific quarantine and regulated non-quarantine pest (RNQP) diseases across four European countries with diverse climates and geological features, extending its reach to New Zealand as well.

Figure 1. STELLA UCPs map

Additionally, a core component of the STELLA project is the elaboration of capacity-building activities to equip farmers, agronomists, and stakeholders with the necessary skills to use the STELLA system and encourage them to adopt eco-friendly crop protection methods.

Policy recommendations generated through the STELLA PSS findings, will be targeted to policy makers and decision makers aiming to support the European Commission's (EC) goals of reducing pesticide use, managing priority plant pest outbreaks and promoting digitalisation of European Union (EU) agriculture and forestry. A networking strategy will be developed to exchange ideas, leverage existing knowledge and enable links with relevant organisations, citizens, networks, projects, and initiatives. Figure 2 showcases the six main pillars of the project: STELLA PSS, STELLA Platform, UCPs, Capacity Building Activities, Networks and Synergies, and Policy.

Figure 2. STELLA main pillars

1.2 STELLA Consortium

The STELLA collaboration employs a multi-actor approach, bringing together 14 partners from seven (7) countries to reinforce this methodology. The group includes academic and research institutions, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in agriculture, business, and policy.

By combining the research and innovation expertise, the technological capabilities as well as the expertise in dissemination and communication, the STELLA consortium can leverage a diverse range of theoretical and practical knowledge to achieve the project's objectives. To facilitate this multi-actor approach, the consortium has adopted a well-structured organisational framework based on the DESCA (Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement) project module, which provides a reliable reference point for the group. The ultimate goal of the STELLA partnership is to effectively address the challenges of plant disease detection and mitigation by engaging all relevant stakeholders in the value chain.

The consortium is well-positioned to deliver the promised results in this GA. Additionally, the consortium possesses substantial expertise in the fields of Social Sciences and Humanities, along with experience in open science practices in research and development. Moreover, the consortium partners have pledged to prioritise gender equality considerations at all stages of research and innovation and ensure implementation throughout their collaboration. To realise its vision, STELLA will bring together organisations from the following sectors:

- 3 European universities (AUA, UCSC, BOKU) with significant capacity and experience in artificial intelligence, remote sensing and spectral imaging (AUA, BOKU), as well as in plant disease modelling (UCSC) and phytopathology (UCSC, AUA), capacity building (AUA, UCSC, BOKU), agricultural & environmental economics analysis (AUA, UCSC, BOKU), robotics and autonomous navigation (AUA).
- 2 Research institutes (ILVO, IFV) with significant expertise in plant and food science, digital transformation as well as expertise in earth observation, IoT, semantic enabled interoperability, data sharing (ILVO) and digital agriculture (IFV).
- 5 SMEs (ACTA, PESSL, EDEN, HORTA, LAL) with expertise in agricultural applied research (ACTA, HORTA, LAL), wireless monitoring systems (PESSL), plant disease detection, AI and data fusion (EDEN), implementation of Decision Support Systems for plant disease prognosis and management (HORTA) and R&D in science and technologies for primary industries (LincolnAgritech).
- 2 NGO Digital Innovation Hubs (AFL, GSC) with expertise in digital transformation, earth observation, IoT and semantic enabled interoperability and digital agriculture.
- 1 Policy consultancy company (GREEN & DIGITAL) with expertise in policy research and development, agriculture and food systems as well as biodiversity and environmental protection.
- 1 Non-profit impact venture studio (FSH) with expertise in impact maximisation as well as business innovation and dissemination.

1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This report presents the first version of Deliverable D6.2: Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication (DEC) Plan, which has been developed within the framework of T6.1: Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan and T6.2: Ecosystem building and stakeholder engagement of WP6: Impact Maximisation and Capacity Building. The aim of the deliverable is to integrate the overall strategy of STELLA, from day one, to define the goals of its DEC activities, to identify the most efficient means to achieve them, and decompose them into a detailed implementation plan. To this end, the DEC plan sets out the objectives, tools, materials, and channels to be exploited to effectively spread STELLA activities, achievements and tangible results to targeted audiences.

This document serves as a reference point for all STELLA's partners when carrying out DEC activities related to the project. Delivered in M06, D6.2 will be updated at M18 (version 2), M32 (version 3) and M48 (version 3), presenting progress on reaching Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as described within.

For the purposes of STELLA, it is necessary to build a vibrant ecosystem around the project. To achieve this, key stakeholders from various sectors have been identified and engaged to

create synergies with relevant EU R&D projects, organisations, and initiatives. This will help in completing the WP6 aim of Ecosystem Building & Stakeholder Engagement.

Additionally, the STELLA DEC Plan aims to set the pace and outline a series of activities designed to effectively target all relevant actors with tailored messages through various means. This approach will maximise actor involvement and alignment while linking STELLA with other projects and initiatives.

The DEC PLAN is outlined in 6 chapters, structured to appropriately present the overall STELLA DEC objectives, strategy, target audiences, tools and means, channels and material for an efficient and effective implementation of dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities within and after the project lifespan.

Table 1. Adherence to STELLA GA deliverable & tasks descriptions

Deliverable D6.2 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan Initial plan presenting the project’s dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan, including the results of their deployment.			
Component Title	Component Outline	Chapter	Description
D6.2: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan	Introduction	Chapter 1	Describes the ongoing STELLA project
	DEC Methodology and Approach	Chapter 2	Describes DEC methodology and approach & DEC time plan
	Dissemination Activities	Chapter 3	Describes STELLA’s dissemination measures & activities & partners’ dissemination KPIs
	Communication Activities	Chapter 4	Describes STELLA’s communication measures & tools and partners’ communication KPIs, target groups and key messages
	Exploitation Activities	Chapter 5	Describes STELLA’s exploitation and IP strategy, along with the project KERs and sustainability plan
	Conclusion	Chapter 6	Presents the conclusions of the deliverable
	Annexes		

2. DEC Methodology and Approach

A well-defined DEC plan is instrumental in maximising the STELLA project's impact and ensuring long-term success. It serves as a roadmap for partners, guiding them in boosting dissemination and communication efforts, raising stakeholder awareness, and achieving impactful results across social, policy, and industry landscapes.

The STELLA DEC plan outlines a comprehensive set of targeted measures for dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC). This multi-actor and multi-channel approach ensures the effective dissemination of project information and outcomes to all identified target groups. By integrating a robust exploitation strategy, the plan fosters ongoing stakeholder engagement and maximises the value of key exploitable results like the STELLA PSS, E-learning platform, and Pest & AI models.

Furthermore, the DEC plan adheres to the GDPR regulations and promotes gender equality, reflecting the project's commitment to social and ethical considerations. Delivered on month 6, the DEC plan will be updated annually. In essence, the DEC plan acts as a blueprint for effectively disseminating project results, exploiting their commercial potential, and executing strategic communication activities. As the leader of Work Package 6, FSH is responsible for coordinating tasks T6.1, T6.2, and T6.4.

2.1 STELLA DEC Time plan

The STELLA DEC plan will be implemented in four distinct phases, each with specific objectives and activities:

- Phase 1: Vision (M01 - M06)

The first phase from M01 to M06 of the project, refers to the vision of the STELLA project, to set the foundation for all subsequent communication, dissemination, and exploitation of STELLA's results. The timeline to develop a comprehensive Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan is set in M06. During this phase, partners will map and outline the target groups for the STELLA ecosystem & engagement bootstrap. In addition, STELLA's visual identity is developed as well as the communication materials for the target audiences.

- Phase 2: Raise Cognition (M07 - M36)

This phase prioritises intensive communication efforts to raise awareness of the project and its benefits among stakeholders. During the second phase, partners will democratise knowledge & enhance the capacities of stakeholders by organising capacity building workshops (2 per UCP), citizen science and demonstration activities.

- Phase 3: Multiplier Effect (M37 - M48)

This third phase focuses on disseminating STELLA PSS, the e-learning platform and the other project results. Partners will organise demonstration events, engage with policymakers, and promote the adoption of project solutions. Additionally, this phase

will explore viable exploitation scenarios and raise awareness of intellectual property rights.

- Phase 4: Sustainability (Year 5 - Year 8)

This final phase focuses on maximising the project's impact beyond its lifespan. During this phase partners will focus on long term exploitation by following the Sustainability plan to identify how the project results are sustained and exploited in the long term and keeping the interest for the STELLA Pest Surveillance System by uploading high-quality content in project's social media platforms and website. Also contributes to further expanding of the STELLA innovation ecosystem.

Figure 3. STELLA DEC implementation time plan

The four-phase implementation of STELLA's DEC plan strategically integrates ecosystem building, targeted stakeholder engagement, and a multi-actor approach to maximise DEC impact. Through a comprehensive dissemination and communication strategy, the plan ensures effective knowledge sharing and project visibility. Planning and reporting procedures guarantee transparency and facilitate continuous improvement. Even after project completion, dissemination and communication activities will sustain momentum. Furthermore, a robust exploitation strategy, coupled with a well-defined sustainability plan and an IPR management framework, will ensure the long-term viability and value of STELLA's results.

2.2 Target Groups and messages

To maximise engagement and the reach of project results, the STELLA project has identified and segmented its target audience into distinct groups. A clear understanding of these target groups, their needs, locations, and characteristics is crucial for developing appropriate communication and dissemination channels, as well as effective activities. Activities across various work packages are designed to gather valuable insights into the needs,

expectations, and motivations of key stakeholders. This information will be integrated into the engagement strategy, which will be further elaborated upon in later versions of the DEC plan.

Six target groups have been identified to comprehensively categorise all parties who may benefit from the project and its outcomes. For each target group, key messages have been crafted to clearly communicate the project's value proposition (Table 2). Additionally, a general breakdown of activities and channels designed to engage each group has been established (Figure 4). These initial steps will pave the way for the development of more comprehensive engagement strategies in future DEC plan updates.

Table 2. Target groups and their key messages

Target Group	Members	Key Message
Agriculture & forestry actors	Individual farmers, foresters, farmers' and forestry cooperatives and associations, agronomists, farmers' advisors	<i>“Get access to cutting-edge technologies and enhance the adoption of plant health, early detection and phytosanitary measures, prevent pest outbreaks and reduce crop losses towards maximised performance, efficiency and stable profit increase”</i>
Policy Makers & regulators	Local, regional and national authorities (e.g. ministries and governments) and EU-DGs (AGRI, ENVI, SANTE, CONNECT, CLIMA), EP Committees (AGRI, ENVI, AIDA)	<i>“Create evidence-based policies facilitating the transition towards a more digitised agriculture and a neutral-pesticide era for an advanced pest surveillance system for quarantine and regulated pests, which are priority pests in EU and globally”</i>
Industry & Technology	Ag-tech companies, SMEs, start-ups, and corporations providing smart agriculture equipment, early warning systems and plant health services, industry associations	<i>“Build upon the STELLA’s novel solutions and exploit the STELLA PSS to integrate new smart solutions to gain competitive advantage benefits”</i>
Research & Academia	Universities, students, faculties and research institutes focused on agriculture and forestry, climate change, smart farming, individual scientists	<i>“Utilise STELLA’s outputs for enhancing scientific knowledge and contribute to the development of cutting-edge early warning, detection, and control system technologies”</i>
Society	Consumers and their associations, citizens and citizens groups, NGOs	<i>“Gain insights on how the deployment of digital technologies can significantly contribute to the reduction of pesticide use supporting plant health and leading to fair, healthy and resilient agriculture and forestry”</i>

Figure 4. STELLA's Ecosystem building - Dissemination & Communication tools

2.3 STELLA DEC Objectives & KPIs

Within STELLA, dissemination and communication activities aim to achieve the desired visibility of the project and build a multi-actor approach ecosystem addressed to all target groups. This will follow a hybrid approach that combines both electronic and non-electronic tools and channels.

2.3.1 DEC Objectives

This section outlines the specific objectives that guide STELLA's efforts in dissemination, communication, and exploitation, ensuring that the project's impact is maximised and its benefits are widely shared.

- **Dissemination Objectives**

The main objective of the STELLA dissemination strategy is to ensure the project's outcomes, knowledge, and opportunities are effectively diffused to the appropriate target communities, making research results widely accessible. More specifically, the dissemination strategy's objectives are to:

- **Engage Stakeholders:** Bring together a critical mass of stakeholders and maximise outreach opportunities for STELLA with targeted messaging and customised content.
- **Knowledge Diffusion:** Disseminate scientific and technological knowledge generated in the project and put it to productive use via capacity building under the STELLA E-learning platform.
- **Utilise Feedback:** Receive and utilise feedback from key stakeholder segments and potential users to ensure project developments are aligned with their needs.
- **Integrate Activities:** Align and integrate dissemination, communication, and community-building activities with exploitation efforts to ensure the sustainability of our reusable assets.
- **Promote Synergies:** Foster synergies with other research, policy, and communication initiatives, leveraging existing networks and channels.

- **Communication Objectives**

STELLA aims to raise public awareness of the project through a range of strategically planned actions that are accessible to internal and external stakeholders, the media, and the general public. The communication strategy will:

- **Content Marketing and Community Building:** Pair focused content marketing with community-building strategies.
- **Raise Awareness:** Raise awareness and facilitate information exchange on data-driven, sustainability-oriented technology innovations.
- **Encourage Acceptability:** Promote the acceptability of these innovations by farmers, their advisors, and policymakers.
- **Reflect Inclusivity:** Ensure that gender equality and inclusivity are reflected in the approach, tools, and channels used.

- Exploitation objectives

STELLA aims to capture the innovation potential and added value of project results, promoting scale-up and replication for far-reaching adoption. The exploitation strategy will:

- **Create Feasible Paths:** Develop practical pathways to deliver project results to stakeholders interested in their use or reuse.
- **Define Key Exploitable Results (KERs):** Elaborate upon and define new KERs to expedite development and commercialization when possible.

2.3.2 KPIs

STELLA DEC KPIs are briefly presented in the following table. Sections 3 and 4 provide a more thorough description along with their target numbers and breakdown.

Table 3. STELLA's Dissemination KPIs

Dissemination KPIs
D1.1 - Peer reviewed open access journal publications
D1.2 - Scientific conference publications
D2.1 - Technical journals and national magazine publications
D2.2 - Datasets via OpenAIRE
D3.1 - Capacity building workshops
D3.2 - Number of participating stakeholders
D3.3 - E-learning platform with 4 modules
D3.4 - E-learning platform hours of training material
D4.1 - Policy Toolbox
D4.2 - Toolbox policy recommendations/briefs supporting plant health policies
D4.3 - Practice abstracts reporting technological innovations
D4.4 - Guide for policy design
D4.5 - Workshop for the STELLA policy network
D5.1 - Participation in conferences
D5.2 - Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives

Table 4. STELLA's Communication KPIs

Communication KPIs
C1.1 - Visual identity & motto
C1.2 - Banners
C1.3 - Brochures
C1.4 - Printing & distribution of promotional materials
C2.1 - Website unique visitors
C2.2 - Blog posts

Communication KPIs
C2.3 - Bounce Rate
C3.1 - Social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, SlideShare, Instagram)
C3.2 - Total audience
C3.3 - Social media posts
C3.4 - Total interactions
C3.5 - Hashtags
C4.1 - E-newsletter subscriptions
C5.1 - Press releases
C5.2 - Press release translations
C5.3 - Videos from the UCPs
C5.4 - Short video/animations
C5.5 - TV/radio interviews

2.4 Multi Actor Approach methodology

The STELLA project employs a Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) to ensure the successful development and implementation of innovative pest management and plant health solutions. This approach is central to STELLA's mission of promoting sustainable agriculture and enhancing biosecurity measures across various agricultural sectors. Here are some key aspects of STELLA's multi-actor approach (Figure 5):

- **Inclusive Stakeholder Engagement:** STELLA brings together a diverse range of stakeholders, including farmers, researchers, industry experts, policymakers, and end-users. This inclusive engagement ensures that the project addresses real-life needs and challenges, leading to practical and effective solutions.
- **Citizen Science and Crowdsourcing:** The project utilises citizen science and crowdsourcing via a smartphone app to capture images and collect human observations at the field level. This approach not only enhances data collection but also broadens stakeholder engagement by involving citizens directly in the monitoring and surveillance of pests.
- **Interactive Innovation Model:** The MAA emphasises the importance of interactive innovation, where the most valuable resources are the diverse types of knowledge and their links. The interactive learning processes that will take place during the UCPs, along with the E-learning platform are central to this model, facilitating collaboration and co-creation among various actors.
- **Participatory Bottom-Up Approach:** STELLA adopts a participatory bottom-up approach, allowing stakeholders to influence project outcomes from decision-making to evaluation. This social process contrasts with traditional top-down scientific approaches, fostering greater stakeholder involvement and ownership.
- **Integrated Work Packages:** The project designates specific work packages and tasks to stimulate discussion with stakeholders from the beginning and utilise their input throughout the project. This integration ensures that end users are included across all work packages, enhancing the relevance and applicability of the project's outcomes.

- **Cross-Sector Collaboration:** STELLA's multi-actor approach facilitates cross-sector collaboration, bringing together diverse yet complementary knowledge and skills. This collaboration is essential for addressing complex agricultural challenges and developing holistic solutions. The project actively seeks synergies and collaboration opportunities with other projects, initiatives, and networks across academia, industry, society, and government.
- **Targeted Communication and Dissemination:** The approach includes targeted communication and dissemination strategies to raise awareness of project activities and results among key stakeholders. Using language, vocabulary, and communication channels that are appealing and appropriate for the audience, the project ensures effective information dispersal. Additionally, the project's website and specific communication materials are translated into the partners' languages to broaden their reach.
- **Sustainable Engagement and Exploitation:** STELLA integrates its dissemination and communication efforts with a sound exploitation strategy, ensuring lasting stakeholder engagement and effective use of key project results. This includes the continuous promotion of the STELLA PSS, E-learning resources, and advanced pest and AI models.

Figure 5. Multi-actor approach

By leveraging the strengths of its multi-actor approach, STELLA aims to achieve significant advancements in pest management, promote sustainable agricultural practices, and enhance the overall resilience of agricultural ecosystems. This collaborative and inclusive strategy is fundamental to the project's success and its ability to create lasting impact.

Key Scenarios

Based on the LIAISON project Practitioner Handbook¹, a series of specific scenarios (Figure 6) and tools have been identified to ensure the effective use of interactive innovation and the multi-actor approach during project implementation. This handbook will serve as a key reference, and additional tools may be utilised as needed.

The adopted multi-actor approach involves tailored strategies for each target group, with specific steps and customised activities designed to achieve maximum impact. This approach aims to contribute significantly to the creation of the STELLA Ecosystem and ensure the overall success and impact of the project.

Figure 6. Multi-actor approach, key scenarios

2.5 Planning reporting and monitoring procedures

Three main actions for all partners designed in order to plan and report all of their activities:

A. Planning

Partners are asked to provide a plan for their dissemination and communications activities each semester through a dedicated spreadsheet with three tables (Annex V):

1. Event Planning: Events that are already in the partner organisations' calendar with relevant local, regional and/or national events.
2. Synergy Mapping: Projects that partners are currently involved in. Working groups, networks, alliances that consortium partners are involved in. Other potential synergy opportunities could be foreseen.
3. Publication Planning: Peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, magazine articles and any other publication partners have planned.

¹ LIAISON (2021) Practitioner Handbook: Evaluation and Impact Assessment of Interactive Innovation. <https://liaison2020.eu/wpcontent/uploads/2021/09/LIAISON-Assessment-Tools.pdf>

B. Reporting

Each month, all partners will be requested to update an online spreadsheet with any communication or dissemination activities that took place and deposit corresponding promoting material such as photos, reports, etc. in a designated folder. This procedure reinforces accountability and engagement with the dissemination and communication process. The results will be compiled and serve to monitor targets and inform DEC strategies as the project progresses. FSH will be responsible for monitoring the KPIs on a monthly basis and provide updates to the rest of the partners at relevant meetings. In case, significant, or repeated deviations are recorded from certain partners, the coordinator will be officially informed. Deviations will have to be justified, discussed among partners, and changes in the DEC strategy will be reported on the updated versions of the DEC plan.

The online spreadsheet (Annex VI) has been developed and uploaded on the project's shared Drive and is available to all partners. This reporting form is designed for the easy input of dissemination and communication activities and will help maintain accountability and engagement with the dissemination and communication process. It includes an instructions section, a sheet with KPI description and breakdown per reporting period, breakdown per partner and one sheet dedicated to each partner. In each one of the latter, the respective participating organisations can see the dissemination and communication activities assigned to them that need to be reported, accordingly, per month of action.

- The **“Instructions”** sheet provides a brief description of the spreadsheet, its purpose, and detailed instructions on how to use it.
- The **“1A - KPIs per RP”** sheet includes the breakdown of the KPIs per reporting period. The purpose of this sheet is to minimise the confusion regarding the scope of each KPI and to assist partners in identifying which KPI their activities correspond to. The focus is on the dissemination KPIs, which often have greater ambiguity.
- The third sheet (**2A - Partner breakdown**) contains a breakdown of the KPIs per partner, based on their expertise, capabilities, and assigned person-months.
- **“3A - Monitoring”** sheet includes various tables that automate the monitoring process using different functions, fed by the partners' input on their dedicated sheets. The purpose of this sheet is to automate, visualise, and simplify the monitoring procedure for all partners.
- The spreadsheet is completed with the partner-dedicated reporting sheets (14 in total), each containing a main Dissemination & Communication (D&C) activities reporting table and a table with the relevant distributed KPI targets and status.

Reporting process

Each partner's dedicated reporting sheet features two tables.

- The first table is the main reporting table, where partners can easily report their monthly activities or indicate that there is nothing to report. This helps both FSH and partner organisations with multiple contributors differentiate between instances of not reporting and not having participated in any relevant activities. The table includes click-and-select options, dropdown menus, hyperlinks, and conditional formatting to streamline the reporting procedure.

Initially, partners are prompted to select the date and type of the activity, followed by providing a short description, a relevant link, and the option to upload any materials (e.g., agendas, presentations, minutes) that may be used for reporting or dissemination purposes. Finally, partners are asked to specify the type and number of stakeholders reached and indicate whether the activity was a joint effort.

On March 27, 2024, FSH organised an online walkthrough for the entire consortium to provide detailed, step-by-step guidance on the reporting procedure, address any questions, and offer support as needed. Additionally, FSH follows up with partners at the end of each month to remind them of the reporting requirements.

- The second table, located on the right side of the dedicated partner sheets, contains the KPIs for which each partner is responsible throughout the project. It includes the assigned target, the current status, and a visual representation to facilitate quick and reliable monitoring of progress. Specifically:
 - "X" Symbol: This symbol indicates that the activity has not yet begun.
 - "Check" Symbol: This symbol signifies that the KPI target has been reached. It confirms that the desired outcome or goal associated with the KPI has been successfully achieved.
 - Hourglass Symbol: This symbol denotes that the activity is ongoing. It represents that work is currently in progress to meet the KPI target, but the goal has not yet been fully accomplished.

Table 5. FSH's assigned KPIs, target and status

KPI	Target	Status
D4 - Policy contribution		
D4.5 - Workshop for the STELLA policy network	0.5	0
D5 - Ecosystem Building		
D5.1 - Participation in conferences	1	0
D5.2 - Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	1	0
C1 - Branding & material		
C1.1 - Visual identity & motto	1	1
C1.2 - Banners	8	1
C1.3 - Brochures	8	1
C1.4 - Printing & distribution of promotional materials	150	0
C2 - Website		
C2.2 - Blog posts	26	1
C2.3 - Bounce Rate	49	58
C3 - Social Platforms		
C3.1 - Social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, SlideShare, Instagram)	6	6
C3.2 - Total audience	1520	390
C3.3 - Social media posts	165	107
C3.4 - Total interactions	10500	1523
C3.5 - Hashtags	5	5

KPI	Target	Status	
C4 - Interactive e-newsletter			
C4.1 - E-newsletter subscriptions	310	27	
C5 - Multimedia			
C5.1 - Press releases	9	1	
C5.2 - Press release translations	9	1	
C5.4 - Short video/animations	11	2	
C5.5 - TV/radio interviews	1	0	

C. Monitoring

For monitoring purposes, a dedicated sheet (within the reporting spreadsheet), named "3A - Monitoring" has been created (Annex VI). This dashboard collects data from partner reports and presents it in a clear and user-friendly format.

This sheet lists all Dissemination & Communication KPIs along with their targets, current status, and progress visualisations (e.g., bar charts). The sheet also includes a dedicated monitoring table for the 1st reporting period. Additional tables for the 2nd and 3rd reporting periods will be added as the project progresses.

In addition to the KPI tables, the dashboard features separate progress tables for each partner. Those tables are also included in the partner's dedicated reporting sheets for convenience.

By collecting data from partner reports and presenting it in a clear and visual format, this dashboard offers several key benefits:

- Enhanced transparency: All stakeholders can easily monitor progress on KPIs, fostering transparency and accountability within the consortium.
- Early identification of issues: Regular monitoring allows for the early identification of any potential roadblocks or areas where communication and dissemination efforts may need to be adjusted.
- Data-driven decision making: The dashboard provides valuable data to inform decision-making regarding resource allocation, communication strategies, and overall DEC plan effectiveness.
- Improved collaboration: By tracking partner contributions and progress, the dashboard facilitates collaboration and ensures all partners are working effectively towards shared goals.

In essence, this monitoring sheet acts as a critical tool for ensuring the STELLA project achieves its maximum impact through its dissemination and communication efforts.

3. Dissemination Activities

The primary goal of the STELLA dissemination strategy is to ensure that the project's outcomes, knowledge, and innovations are effectively communicated to and embraced by the relevant target communities. By making research results widely accessible, STELLA aims to maximise its impact and foster a broad understanding and adoption of its results. The dissemination strategy is designed to achieve the following specific objectives:

- **Introduce the STELLA solutions:** Showcase the STELLA Pest Surveillance System and its innovative tools to key stakeholders, enhancing visibility and understanding of the project's objectives and achievements.
- **Leverage Field Test Results:** Capitalise on the insights and impacts derived from the in-field tests, highlighting the real-world applications and benefits of STELLA solutions.
- **Promote Synergies:** Foster collaborations with other research projects, policy initiatives, and communication campaigns by utilising existing dissemination networks and channels to amplify the reach of STELLA's messages.
- **Engage and Validate:** Actively engage with targeted audiences to gather feedback, validate findings, and ensure the applicability, replicability, and scalability of project results across different contexts.
- **Support Continuous Exploitation:** Ensure the ongoing use and impact of project results in future research, public policy, and other relevant initiatives by creating a robust and sustainable dissemination framework.

3.1 Dissemination KPIs

Table 6 on the next page shows the Dissemination KPIs, including their allocation among partners and reporting periods..

Table 6. Partners' Dissemination KPIs

KPI	Target	AUA	UCSC	EV ILVO	BOKU	GREEN & DIGITAL	FSH	ACTA	HORTA SRL	PESSL	GSC	AFL	EDEN CORE	IFV	Lincoln Agritech
D1 - Scientific Publications															
D1.1 - Peer reviewed open access journal publications	>12	3	3	3	2									2	
D1.2 - Scientific conference publications	>15	4	3	3	4									2	
D2 - Technical Publications															
D2.1 - Technical journals and national magazine publications	>10	2	1	2	1			1	1				1	1	1
D2.2 - Datasets via OpenAIRE	>50		51												
D3 - Capacity Building															
D3.1 - Capacity building workshops	>12	2	2		3							2		2	2
D3.2 - Number of participating stakeholders	>150	52	26		26							26		26	26
D3.3 - E-learning platform with 4 modules	1	1													
D3.4 - E-learning platform hours of training material	>12	13													
D4 - Policy contribution															
D4.1 - Policy Toolbox	1					1									
D4.2 - Toolbox policy recommendations/briefs supporting plant health policies	>5					6									
D4.3 - Practice abstracts reporting technological innovations	>60					61									
D4.4 - Guide for policy design	1					1									
D4.5 - Workshop for the STELLA policy network	1					0.5	0.5								
D5 - Ecosystem Building															
D5.1 - Participation in conferences	>10	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
D5.2 - Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	>8	4	1	1	1		1							1	

All the KPIs have been distributed in the relevant reporting periods based on the project's timeline and in accordance with the DEC plan strategy (Table 7).

Table 7. KPI distribution per reporting period

KPI	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
D1 - Scientific Publications				
D1.1 - Peer reviewed open access journal publications	>12	0	6	7
D1.2 - Scientific conference publications	>15	0	8	8
D2 - Technical Publications				
D2.1 - Technical journals and national magazine publications	>10	2	5	4
D2.2 - Datasets via OpenAIRE	>50	0	25	26
D3 - Capacity Building				
D3.1 - Capacity building workshops	>12	3	10	0
D3.2 - Number of participating stakeholders	>150	75	107	0
D3.3 - E-learning platform with 4 modules	1	0	1	0
D3.4 - E-learning platform hours of training material	>12	0	5	8
D4 - Policy contribution				
D4.1 - Policy Toolbox	1	0	0	1
D4.2 - Toolbox policy recommendations/briefs supporting plant health policies	>5	0	0	6
D4.3 - Practice abstracts reporting technological innovations	>60	20	0	41
D4.4 - Guide for policy design	1	0	0	1
D4.5 - Workshop for the STELLA policy network	1	0	0	1
D5 - Ecosystem Building				
D5.1 - Participation in conferences	>10	3	6	5
D5.2 - Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	>8	3	4	2

3.2 Dissemination Measures and Tools

The Dissemination measures of STELLA refer to target groups such scientists, authorities, policy makers, industry, sectors of interest and is based on customised measures that includes publications, capacity building & policy contribution.

3.2.1 Scientific Publications

This KPI category aims to democratise scientific knowledge by making publicly available STELLA's results for the research community for future research on digital technologies supporting plant health early detection, territory surveillance and phytosanitary measures. It includes:

- **>12 Peer reviewed open access journal publications.**
 - Scholarly papers that have undergone evaluation by field experts. These research papers should be open access.

- **> 15 Scientific conference publications.**
 - Conference contributions not necessarily in peer reviewed journals that can fall within other scientific, policy and/or industry platforms.

Table 8. Scientific Publications KPIs per partner

KPI	Target	AUA	UCSC	EV ILVO	BOKU	IFV
D1 - Scientific Publications						
D1.1 - Peer reviewed open access journal publications	>12	3	3	3	2	2
D1.2 - Scientific conference publications	>15	4	3	3	4	2

Table 9. Scientific Publications KPIs per reporting period

KPI	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
D1 - Scientific Publications				
D1.1 - Peer reviewed open access journal publications	>12		6	7
D1.2 - Scientific conference publications	>15		8	8

3.2.2 Technical Publications

Technical publications for Agriculture and forestry actors, Policy makers, Industry and Technology, Research & Academia t to technical blog posts, articles, position/white papers, catalogues, books and other publications for relevant innovations and research derived from project activities, workshops, Use Case Pilots. This category includes:

- **>10 Technical journals and national magazine publications.**
 - Publication of technical briefs in renowned national magazines that specialise in the relevant project fields.
- **Datasets via OpenAIRE.**
 - Image & numeric/ tabular datasets about pest/disease occurrence, site specifications and management shared via OpenAIRE platform.

Table 10. Technical Publications KPIs per partner

KPI	Target	AUA	UCSC	EV ILVO	BOKU	ACTA	HORTA SRL	EDEN CORE	IFV	Lincoln Agritech
D2 - Technical Publications										
D2.1 - Technical journals and national magazine publications	>10	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
D2.2 - Datasets via OpenAIRE	>50		51							

Table 11. Technical Publications KPIs per reporting period

KPI	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
D2 - Technical Publications				
D2.1 - Technical journals and national magazine publications	>10	2	5	4
D2.2 - Datasets via OpenAIRE	>50		25	26

3.2.3 Capacity Building

Stella project will strengthen stakeholders' capacity to capitalise STELLA PSS and its three subsystems through capacity building workshops and a multimodal asynchronous e-learning platform:

- **>12 Capacity building workshops.**
 - Interactive sessions designed to provide participants with practical skills, knowledge, and experiences. Workshops will take place within the UCPs (1 per year) in order to increase digital technologies deployment and support key factors (e.g. data, training needs) needed for adopting these technologies.
- **>150 Participating stakeholders.**
 - More than 25 stakeholders are expected to be involved in each UCP.
- **1 E-learning platform with 4 modules.**
 - Multimodal platform offering free, online training material towards strengthening the capacities of stakeholders in adopting STELLA's results.
- **>12 E-learning platform hours of training material.**
 - Asynchronous learning material for targeted stakeholders combining visual elements, images, figures and text.

Table 12. Capacity Building KPIs per partner

KPI	Target	AUA	UCSC	BOKU	AFL	IFV	Lincoln Agritech
D3 - Capacity Building							
D3.1 - Capacity building workshops	>12	2	2	3	2	2	2
D3.2 - Number of participating stakeholders	>150	52	26	26	26	26	26
D3.3 - E-learning platform with 4 modules	1	1					
D3.4 - E-learning platform hours of training material	>12	13					

Table 13. Capacity Building KPIs per reporting period

KPI	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
D3 - Capacity Building				
D3.1 - Capacity building workshops	>12	3	10	
D3.2 - Number of participating stakeholders	>150	75	107	
D3.3 - E-learning platform with 4 modules	1		1	
D3.4 - E-learning platform hours of training material	>12		5	8

3.2.4 Policy contribution

To achieve high-scale and long-lasting impact, a toolbox, including policy recommendations and practice abstracts, will be developed towards the empowerment of EU's and Associated Countries' policies on safeguarding plants' health, as well as on the promotion of the digitalization of agriculture. Guidelines will be provided for entering the non-pesticide usage era, while frameworks for managing priority plant pest outbreaks will be elaborated. This category includes the following KPIs:

- **1 Policy Toolbox.**
 - Aimed at policymakers operating at different levels, and covering the importance of effective plant-health management, embracing new technologies in territory surveillance, establishing diagnostic networks, and the use of digital technologies in supporting plant health policies.
- **>5 Toolbox policy recommendations/briefs supporting plant health policies .**
 - To achieve high-scale and long-lasting impact, a toolbox, including policy recommendations and practice abstracts, will be developed towards the empowerment of EU's and Associated Countries' policies on safeguarding plants' health, as well as on the promotion of the digitalization of agriculture.
- **>60 Practice abstracts reporting technological innovations.**
 - Practice abstracts aimed at policymakers operating at different levels.
- **1 Guide for policy design.**
 - Policy roadmap to assist policy makers adopting digital technologies to support plant health policies and ensure that policy interventions are based on sound research.
- **1 Workshop for the STELLA policy network.**
 - A workshop for the STELLA policy network and beyond will be organised in Brussels, bringing policy makers together to discuss and learn about the policy recommendations.

Table 14. Policy Contribution KPIs per partner

KPI	Target	GREEN & DIGITAL	FSH
D4 - Policy contribution			
D4.1 - Policy Toolbox	1	1	
D4.2 - Toolbox policy recommendations/briefs supporting plant health policies	>5	6	
D4.3 - Practice abstracts reporting technological innovations	>60	61	
D4.4 - Guide for policy design	1	1	
D4.5 - Workshop for the STELLA policy network	1	0.5	0.5

Table 15. Policy Contribution KPIs per reporting period

KPI	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
D4 - Policy contribution				
D4.1 - Policy Toolbox	1			1
D4.2 - Toolbox policy recommendations/briefs supporting plant health policies	>5			6
D4.3 - Practice abstracts reporting technological innovations	>60	20		41
D4.4 - Guide for policy design	1			1
D4.5 - Workshop for the STELLA policy network	1			1

3.2.5 Ecosystem Building

A vibrant, expanding community of stakeholders will be nurtured with engagement stimulated through an extensive presence in national, European and international trade fairs and exhibitions and facilitate strategic synergies and partnerships with other EU-funded projects (e.g. OPTIMA, Farmtopia), R&I networks/ platforms, incl EIP-AGRI & Thematic Networks; EIP-AGRI Operational Groups:

- 10 Participations in conferences.
 - Representation of STELLA at various events: poster or speaker at a conference, presentation, brochure distribution, banner or booth at fairs/expos, panellist or discussion participant in forum.
- >8 Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives.
 - Engage in collaborative endeavours with EU initiatives/projects to leverage collective expertise, share best practices, and maximise the impact of efforts in the field of the relevant fields.

Table 16. Ecosystem Building KPIs per partner

KPI	Target	AUA	UCSC	EV ILVO	BOKU	GREEN & DIGITAL	FSH	ACTA	HORTA SRL	PESSL	GSC	AFL	EDEN CORE	IFV	Lincoln Agritech
D5 - Ecosystem Building															
D5.1 - Participation in conferences	>10	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
D5.2 - Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	>8	4	1	1	1		1							1	

Table 17. Ecosystem Building KPIs per reporting period

KPI	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
D5 - Ecosystem Building				
D5.1 - Participation in conferences	>10	3	6	5
D5.2 - Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	>8	3	4	2

4. Communication Activities

A comprehensive communication strategy is essential to ensure that all relevant stakeholders receive clear and consistent messages. This strategy outlines the communication activities to be undertaken throughout the project's duration and beyond, aiming to foster public engagement, disseminate knowledge, and maximise the project's overall impact. Key Components:

- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Identify key stakeholders and tailor messages to meet their needs for active participation.
- **Communication Channels and Tools:** Utilise traditional media (press releases, print) and digital media (social media, website, newsletters). Organise events and workshops for direct interaction.
- **Content Development and Dissemination Strategy:** Develop clear core messages and create content (articles, blogs, infographics, videos) to effectively disseminate them. Plan dissemination timing, frequency, and channels.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Establish KPIs (website traffic, social media engagement, event participation eg.) and track them to implement feedback mechanisms. Refine efforts, assess, and adjust strategies for maximum impact.
- **Sustainability and Continuity:** Ensure ongoing communication post-project and facilitate knowledge transfer to other initiatives.

4.1 Communication KPIs

To achieve the desired impact for the STELLA project, a hybrid approach will be implemented, integrating both traditional and digital tools, methods, and channels. Specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will guide our efforts as defined in the STELLA project plan. By monitoring these KPIs, we can continuously refine and optimise our communication activities to ensure maximum impact and outreach. All the Communication KPIs have been distributed in the relevant reporting periods based on the project's timeline and in accordance with the DEC plan strategy and will be executed as follows:

Table 18. Partners' Communication KPIs

KPI	Target	AUA	UCSC	EV ILVO	BOKU	GREEN & DIGITAL	FSH	ACTA	HORTA SRL	PESSL	GSC	AFL	EDEN CORE	IFV	Lincoln Agritech
C1 - Branding & material															
C1.1 - Visual identity & motto	1						1								
C1.2 - Banners	>7						8								
C1.3 - Brochures	>7						8								
C1.4 - Printing & distribution of promotional materials	>2000	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
C2 - Website															
C2.1 - Website unique visitors	>15000	0					15100								
C2.2 - Blog posts	>50	6	1	2	1	2	26	1	2	1	4	2	1	1	1
C2.3 - Bounce Rate	<50						49								
C3 - Social Platform															
C3.1 - Social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, SlideShare, Instagram)	6						6								
C3.2 - Total audience	>1500						1520								
C3.3 - Social media posts	>160						165								
C3.4 - Total interactions	>10000						10500								
C3.5 - Hashtags	5						5								
C4 - Interactive e-newsletter															
C4.1 - E-newsletter subscriptions	>300						310								
C5 - Multimedia															
C5.1 - Press releases	>8						9								
C5.2 - Press release translations	63			9	9		18	9	9		9				
C5.3 - Videos from the UCPs	>6	2	1		1							1		1	1
C5.4 - Short video/animations	>10						11								
C5.5 - TV/radio interviews	>5	1	1		1		1					1		1	

Table 19. Communication KPIs distribution per reporting period

KPIs	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
C1 - Branding & material				
C1.1 - Visual identity & motto	1	1	0	0
C1.2 - Banners	>7	1	6	1
C1.3 - Brochures	>7	1	6	1
C1.4 - Printing & distribution of promotional materials	>2000	300	950	850
C2 - Website				
C2.1 - Website unique visitors	>15000	3000	7000	5100
C2.2 - Blog posts	>50	15	20	16
C2.3 - Bounce Rate	<50	49	49	49
C3 - Social Platforms				
C3.1 - Social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, SlideShare, Instagram)	6	6	0	0
C3.2 - Total audience	>1500	400	500	620
C3.3 - Social media posts	>160	50	60	55
C3.4 - Total interactions	>10000	3000	4500	3000
C3.5 - Hashtags	5	5	0	0
C4 - Interactive e-newsletter				
C4.1 - E-newsletter subscriptions	>300	100	120	90
C5 - Multimedia				
C5.1 - Press releases	>8	3	4	2
C5.2 - Press release translations	63	21	68	14
C5.3 - Videos from the UCPs	>6	0	5	2
C5.4 - Short video/animations	>10	3	5	3
C5.5 - TV/radio interviews	>5	1	3	2

4.2 Communication Measures and Tools

STELLA has implemented a comprehensive communication strategy to ensure that project results are widely disseminated and stakeholder engagement is maximised. This strategy utilises a multi-channel approach, including targeted promotional materials such as brochures and banners, a dynamic and informative online presence through a website and newsletters, multimedia such as videos and interviews, and a strategic social media presence across 6 platforms (LinkedIn, Facebook, X, YouTube, Instagram, SlideShare). This integrated approach ensures effective knowledge exchange and promotes the long-term impact of the project's findings.

4.2.1 Branding & material

STELLA's branding strategy focuses on creating a strong, memorable identity that visually represents the project's goals and values. This involves developing a cohesive visual identity and producing high-quality communication materials. The branding strategy includes the creation of a distinctive logo, consistent colour schemes, and typography guidelines.

Additionally, templates for presentations, deliverables, reports, and other documentation have been produced to ensure uniformity. Communication materials such as banners and brochures will be designed to reinforce the project's presence at events and online.

- **1 Visual identity & 1 motto**
 - The visual identity of STELLA is crafted to be distinct and easily recognizable, incorporating specific colours, fonts, and logo designs that reflect the project's innovative spirit ([Annex II](#)).
 - The project's motto: "Cultivating the Future with AI for Plant Health", encapsulates its mission and vision, serving as a succinct representation of its core objectives.
- **>7 Banners**
 - Eye-catching and informative banners will be a key promotional tool for STELLA. They will be used extensively at events to showcase the project's activities, vision, and achievements. A series of eight banners is scheduled to be designed. The first banner, located in [Annex II](#), provides a comprehensive overview of the project. Subsequent banners will delve deeper into the individual Use Case Pilots (UCPs) and the project's results.
- **> 7 Brochures**
 - Brochures contain detailed information about STELLA's objectives, methodologies, and outcomes ([Annex II](#)). They will be distributed at events, meetings, and through digital channels to ensure broad dissemination. The brochures will be translated into partner languages (Dutch, French, German, Greek, Italian and Lithuanian) by dedicated partners, to reach diverse audiences in different regions, ensuring that the key messages of the project are effectively communicated and accessible to a broader audience. STELLA's first brochure can be found in ([Annex II](#)) with another 7 to follow.
- **>2000 Printing & distribution of promotional materials**
 - Distributed promotional materials, including posters and brochures, will be created to increase awareness about the STELLA project. To maximise outreach, STELLA partners will strategically distribute these materials at relevant events, conferences, and workshops. Additionally, digital versions of the materials will be available on the STELLA website and shared through social media channels, allowing for wider dissemination and engagement with the target audiences.

By combining traditional print media with digital outreach and local partnerships, the STELLA project aims to create a comprehensive and inclusive communication strategy that engages diverse communities and stakeholders across various regions.

Table 20. Branding & material KPIs per partner

KPI	Target	AUA	UCSC	EV ILVO	BOKU	GREEN & DIGITAL	FSH	ACTA	HORTA SRL	PESSL	GSC	AFL	EDEN CORE	IFV	Lincoln Agritech
C1 - Branding & material															
C1.1 - Visual identity & motto	1						1								
C1.2 - Banners	>7						8								
C1.3 - Brochures	>7						8								
C1.4 - Printing & distribution of promotional materials	>2000	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

Table 21. Branding & material KPIs per reporting period

KPIs	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
C1 - Branding & material				
C1.1 - Visual identity & motto	1	1	0	0
C1.2 - Banners	>7	1	6	1
C1.3 - Brochures	>7	1	6	1
C1.4 - Printing & distribution of promotional materials	>2000	300	950	850

4.2.2 Website

The STELLA website is the main access point for project information, updates, and resources. It is user-friendly and regularly updated with the latest news, publications, and events related to the project. Visitors can easily navigate the website to find specific information and subscribe to receive updates via email. Additionally, the website facilitates communication through a dedicated contact form.

Figure 7. STELLA website

Website Menu Description

Home Screen: The home screen features the STELLA project logo, full name, and motto, and presents the project's primary objectives. This page also includes a project overview, highlighting its innovative approaches and impact. At the bottom, visitors can find partner logos with clickable links, social media icons, a newsletter signup option, and contact information for the Project Coordinator, Project Manager, and Communication Manager. In addition, home page menu includes the following sub-menus:

- **About Us:** This section provides detailed information about the STELLA project, including its aims, mission, and the challenges that STELLA project has to face.
- **Our Vision:** This section outlines the project's vision, focusing on the Holistic Digital System, Novel Monitoring Strategies, real-life UCPs, and how it will strengthen stakeholders' capacity.
- **Results:** This section showcases the project's outcomes, including key findings, data, and the impact of implemented solutions on pest management and plant health.
- **Target Groups:** Information about the specific groups targeted by the project, such as agriculture and forestry actors, policy makers and regulators, industry and technology, research and academia, and society.

Partners: This section showcases a comprehensive list of all project partners, highlighting the collaborative efforts driving the initiative. It features their logos, detailed descriptions, roles within the project, and links to their respective websites. Additionally, contact information for their communication representatives is provided.

Use Case Pilots: This section details the various UCPs that will be conducted in different regions, showcasing real-world applications and testing of STELLA's solutions in vineyards, forests, arable lands, and orchards across Europe and New Zealand.

Newsroom: This section will contain project updates, press releases, blog posts, and event announcements to keep stakeholders informed about the latest developments and progress.

Resources: Visitors can access a wealth of resources here, including public deliverables, publications, and a media kit designed to provide comprehensive information about the project.

Contact: This section offers detailed contact information for the project team, including the Project Coordinator, Project Manager, and Communication Manager along with a contact form for facilitating direct communication with stakeholders.

PSS Platform: This section will provide information about the STELLA PSS platform, its functionalities, and how it supports the project's objectives.

- **>15000 Website unique visitors**
 - The website's performance is monitored using Google Analytics Tool to track unique visitors, ensuring that the site reaches a broad and engaged audience. This metric indicates the number of unique visitors to the STELLA website. From January 2024 to May 2024, 459 users visited the Stella website.
- **>50 Blog posts**
 - Regular blog posts will be published on the STELLA website, providing in-depth insights into project developments, case studies, and expert opinions. These posts aim to keep stakeholders informed and engaged with the project's progress. The target is to publish more than 50 blog posts throughout the project's duration, with 1 post already published so far. A consistent stream of content will ensure continuous engagement and up-to-date information dissemination to all interested parties.
- **<50 Bounce Rate**
 - Bounce Rate: Bounce rate is a metric used in website traffic analysis to measure the percentage of visitors who land on a single page and then leave the website without visiting any other pages. In other words, it reflects the number of visitors who "bounced" away from your site after just one page. Bounce rate is calculated by dividing the number of single-page sessions by the total number of sessions on your website. It's typically expressed as a percentage.
Regular updates and fresh content will aim to keep visitors interested and encourage them to explore the STELLA website further. Interactive elements, such as blog posts, videos, and infographics, will be incorporated to enhance user engagement and reduce the bounce rate.
Additionally, the website has recently been translated from the relative partners into their respective languages (Dutch, French, German, Greek, Italian and Lithuanian) to make it more accessible and appealing to a broader audience. This multilingual approach aims to attract and retain visitors from various regions, fostering a more inclusive and engaging online environment.

Table 22. Website KPIs per partner

KPI	Target	AUA	UCSC	EV ILVO	BOKU	GREEN & DIGITAL	FSH	ACTA	HORTA SRL	PESSL	GSC	AFL	EDEN CORE	IFV	Lincoln Agritech
C2 - Website															
C2.1 - Website unique visitors	>15000						1510								
C2.2 - Blog posts	>50	6	1	2	1	2	26	1	2	1	4	2	1	1	1
C2.3 - Bounce Rate	<50						49								

Table 23. Website KPIs per reporting period

KPIs	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
C2 - Website				
C2.1 - Website unique visitors	>15000	3000	7000	5100
C2.2 - Blog posts	>50	15	20	16
C2.3 - Bounce Rate	<50	49	49	49

4.2.3 Social Platforms

- **6 Social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, X, YouTube, SlideShare, Instagram)**
 - STELLA leverages various social media platforms to maximise its reach and stakeholder engagement. With accounts already established on LinkedIn, Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), YouTube, SlideShare, and Instagram, aiming to disseminate information, share project updates, and foster stakeholder interaction.
- **>1500 Total audience**
 - The total audience across all social media channels is tracked to measure the reach and impact of STELLA's communication efforts. The target is to reach an audience of more than 1.500 users with the current audience count at 390. This tracking helps in assessing the effectiveness of the outreach strategies and guides adjustments to enhance engagement and visibility.
- **>160 Social media posts**
 - Regular social media posts are scheduled to maintain visibility and engagement with the audience. These posts include updates on project milestones, event announcements, and relevant industry news. The target is to publish more than 160 posts throughout the project's duration, with 97 posts published so far. This consistent posting strategy ensures continuous interaction and keeps the audience well-informed about the project's activities and progress.
- **>10.000 Total interactions**
 - The total interactions on social media posts, including likes, shares, comments, and views, are monitored to gauge the effectiveness of the communication strategy. The target is to achieve more than 10.000 interactions, with 1.523 interactions recorded so far. This monitoring helps in assessing audience engagement and refining the communication approach to better connect with stakeholders and enhance the project's visibility.
- **5 Hashtags**
 - The project improves its discoverability by using specific hashtags such as #pests, #planthealth, #quarantinepests, #pathogendetection, and #phytosanitary, ensuring that the content reaches a targeted and engaged audience interested in these areas. In addition, the hashtags #HorizonEurope and #ResearchImpactEU are suggested by the European Commission.

Social Platforms & Guidelines

Each platform is utilised for its unique strengths (Figure 8): LinkedIn for professional networking, Facebook for broader community engagement, X for real-time updates, YouTube for video content, SlideShare for presentations, and Instagram for visual

storytelling. These efforts ensure a comprehensive and multi-faceted approach to stakeholder communication.

STELLA is using the consortium's established social media networks to maximise the visibility and impact of the project's progress and outcomes. Partners are expected to share and publish content from the project's social media accounts and website. This is mutually beneficial, as it increases traction for project-related work and boosts traffic on partners' pages and social media.

Figure 8. Utilised social media demographics & purpose

When creating social media content, it's essential to consider several parameters:

- Interactivity. This approach ensures that the content effectively reaches and engages the audience. The content should be easily understood by non-specialists, fostering interaction and broadening the project's reach.
- Eye-catching and visually attractive posts are more likely to increase engagement. Prioritising visuals and graphics will make the content stand out.
- Ensuring adaptability of social media formatting and functionality on different devices, particularly mobile phones, is crucial.
- Consistency of messaging and branding across all posts is key. This includes maintaining a consistent tone of voice, style, and visual identity, which helps build a recognizable and trustworthy presence.
- Posts should be timely, both in terms of regular frequency and sharing information as close to the event's date as possible.

Social Media DOs & DON'Ts

A set of social media recommendations (Figure 9) has been compiled to assist partners and facilitate their effective use of social media in order to increase the project's visibility.

Figure 9. Social media DO's & DON'Ts

STELLA's Social media channels

LinkedIn stands out as a premier social media platform for connecting with and engaging professionals. It facilitates sharing information on current trends, innovations, and best practices across various fields. LinkedIn also serves as a platform for connecting academia and industry. STELLA utilises LinkedIn to provide project updates such as partner activities, results progress, and publications. STELLA's LinkedIn page (Figure 10) can be accessed [here](#).

Figure 10. STELLA's LinkedIn page

LinkedIn Analytics offer data on professional network and content performance, including:

- Followers: The number of professionals following a company's page for updates and insights.
- Engagement: User interactions with content, such as likes, comments, shares, saves, and reactions, indicating audience interest.
- Demographics: Information about followers, including job titles, seniority, company size, industry, and location.

Figure 11 illustrates the total number of interactions on the STELLA LinkedIn page from January 2024 to May 2024, which reached 862. Despite its short timeframe, this high level of interaction indicates that the content shared on the STELLA LinkedIn page resonated well with followers, effectively sparking conversations and interest.

Figure 11. LinkedIn interaction metrics

Figure 12 represents the total number of followers on the STELLA page between January 2024 - May 2024, which has reached 223.

Figure 12. LinkedIn follower metrics

Facebook is one of the world's largest social media platforms, with approximately 2.93 billion monthly active users as of the second quarter of 2022. Its audience has an even gender distribution, and the majority of users are aged between 18 - 44². This demographic is dynamic, actively involved, and more likely to engage with new technologies. STELLA's Facebook page can be accessed [here](#).

²Statista. (2024, May 22). Facebook: distribution of global audiences 2024, by age and gender. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/376128/facebook-global-user-age-distribution/>

Figure 13. STELLA's Facebook page

Meta Business Suite provides page statistics for any time range from the page's creation to the present. Metrics include:

- **Reach:** The estimated number of people who saw content from the STELLA page, counted once per person from both organic and paid distribution.
- **Content Interactions:** The number of likes, reactions, saves, comments, shares, and replies on content, including ads.
- **Followers:** The number of people who follow the STELLA page, calculated as total follows minus unfollows till this moment.

STELLA's Facebook page analytics:

Figure 14 covers the period from January 1, 2024, to May 31, 2024, displaying cumulative data. Key metrics shown are:

- **Reach:** 800
- **Content Interactions:** 299
- **Followers:** 55

The graph at the bottom shows the daily breakdown of reach, distinguishing between organic reach and reach from ads. All the reach in this period is from organic sources, with no contribution from ads.

Figure 14. Facebook page metrics

Instagram has over 2 billion monthly active users³, with an almost equal gender split. Dominated by Millennials and Gen Z, it serves as a hub for trends and visual content. This large and diverse user base solidifies Instagram's position as one of the leading social media platforms. STELLA's Instagram page can be accessed [here](#).

Figure 15. STELLA's Instagram page

STELLA's Instagram page analytics:

Figure 16 covers the period from January 1, 2024, to May 31, 2024, displaying cumulative data. Key metrics shown are:

³ Dean, B. (2023, August 18). 133 Super interesting social Marketing media stats (2023). Backlinko. <https://backlinko.com/social-media-marketing-stats>

- **Reach: 349**
- **Content Interactions: 146**
- **Followers: 56**

Figure 16. Instagram metrics

X is an optimal platform for sharing the latest news and trends on varied topics and starting online conversations with audiences worldwide. X's 280-character limit makes news updates quick and easy to digest, and with an average of 330 million active monthly users it is a valuable social media channel for answering project questions with immediacy. STELLA's X page (Figure 17) can be accessed [here](#).

Figure 17. STELLA's X page

Figure 18 displays monthly performance summaries for the STELLA account from January 2024 to May 2024. Each month is broken down with key metrics, and the sum of impressions is 1.476.

Figure 18. X page metrics

YouTube has over 2.5 billion monthly users⁴, making it the world's second largest search engine after Google. With billions of daily views, it solidifies its position as the top platform for engaging video content. The STELLA project account (Figure 19) currently has 29 subscribers.

STELLA's YouTube channel page can be accessed [here](#).

⁴ Kemp, S. (2022, May 4). *Digital 2022: YouTube's ad reach passes 2.5 billion* — DataReportal – Global Digital Insights. DataReportal – Global Digital Insights. <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2022-youtube-headlines?rq=youtube>

Figure 19. STELLA's YouTube channel

SlideShare is an online platform for sharing professional content through presentations, infographics, documents, or videos. With forty content categories, users can easily find information on their topics of interest. It is a valuable channel for professionals and academics to share research findings, industry insights, or educational materials with a global audience. STELLA's SlideShare account can be accessed [here](#).

Figure 20. STELLA's SlideShare page

Table 24. Social Platforms KPIs per partner

KPI	Target	FSH
C3 - Social Platform		
C3.1 - Social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, SlideShare, Instagram)	6	6
C3.2 - Total audience	>1500	1520
C3.3 - Social media posts	>160	165
C3.4 - Total interactions	>10000	10500
C3.5 - Hashtags	5	5

Table 25. Social Platforms KPIs per reporting period

KPIs	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
C3 - Social Platforms				
C3.1 - Social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, SlideShare, Instagram)	6	6	0	0
C3.2 - Total audience	>1500	400	500	620
C3.3 - Social media posts	>160	50	60	55
C3.4 - Total interactions	>10000	3000	4500	3000
C3.5 - Hashtags	5	5	0	0

4.2.4 Interactive e-newsletter

Eight newsletters will be published once every six months, with the first scheduled for June 2024. The newsletter will provide updates and relevant information about the project to subscribers and consortium members throughout the project duration.

Each issue will feature the latest developments, activities, upcoming events, milestones, and insightful reports and publications pertinent to the project. The target audience includes Agriculture & Forestry actors, Policy Makers & Regulators, Industry & Technology professionals, Research & Academia, and Society at large. Newsletter subscription is facilitated through the project’s website via an easy fill-in box for a friendly user experience. MailChimp platform is used to distribute the newsletters.

- **>300 E-newsletter subscriptions**
 - Strategic planning is in place to increase e-newsletter subscriptions through various channels. This ensures a growing number of stakeholders receive regular updates from STELLA. Currently, there are 27 subscribers, with a target of over 300 till the end of the project.

Table 26. Interactive e-newsletter KPIs per partner

KPI	Target	FSH
C4 - Interactive e-newsletter		
C4.1 - E-newsletter subscriptions	>300	310

Table 27. Interactive e-newsletter KPIs per reporting period

KPIs	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
C4 - Interactive e-newsletter				
C4.1 - E-newsletter subscriptions	>300	100	120	90

4.2.5 Multimedia

STELLA uses multimedia content, including videos and animations, to effectively communicate complex information in an engaging and accessible manner.

- **>8 Press releases**
 - STELLA will generate a minimum of 8 press releases to provide information about the key activities implemented and to share important updates related to project milestones, and more. Project’s first press release was published in February 2024 after the successful kick-off meeting which took place in Athens, Greece.

- **54 Press release translations (in total)**
 - Press releases will be translated into partners' languages to ensure the information is accessible to a broad audience across different regions. The first press release has already been translated into the project partners' languages, (Dutch, French, German, Greek, Italian and Lithuanian) enhancing reach and engagement with diverse stakeholders. This approach ensures that all relevant audiences are well-informed about the project's milestones and developments, fostering a broader understanding and support for STELLA's initiatives.

- **>6 Videos from the UCPs**
 - Videos from the UCPs will highlight the practical applications and impacts of the STELLA project. The target is to create more than 6 videos, at least one for each UCP.

- **>10 Short video/animations**
 - Short videos and animations will be created to explain important concepts and results in a visually appealing and concise manner. These will be shared on the website and social media channels. The goal is to produce more than 10 videos with two already produced by FSH.

- **>5 TV/radio interviews**
 - TV and radio interviews with project representatives will be conducted to reach broader audiences and increase public awareness about STELLA's objectives and achievement. This approach allows us to effectively disseminate project findings and advancements, while fostering public interest and support for STELLA's goals.

Table 28. Multimedia KPIs per partner

KPI	Target	AUA	UCSC	EV ILVO	BOKU	FSH	ACTA	HORTA SRL	AFL	IFV	Lincoln Agritech
C5 - Multimedia											
C5.1 - Press releases	>8					9					
C5.2 - Press release translations	63			9	9	18	9	9	9		
C5.3 - Videos from the UCPs	>6	2	1		1				1	1	1
C5.4 - Short video/animations	>10					11					
C5.5 - TV/radio interviews	>5	1	1		1	1			1	1	

Table 29. Multimedia KPIs per reporting period

KPIs	Target	RP1 (1-18)	RP2 (19-36)	RP3 (37-48)
C5 - Multimedia				
C5.1 - Press releases	>8	3	4	2
C5.2 - Press release translations	63	21	68	14
C5.3 - Videos from the UCPs	>6	0	5	2
C5.4 - Short video/animations	>10	3	5	3
C5.5 - TV/radio interviews	>5	1	3	2

5. Exploitation Activities

STELLA will produce several commercial and non-commercial Key Exploitable Results (KERs) over the duration of the project. This chapter will introduce the preliminary results identified during the proposal stage and outline potential pathways for their exploitation. Additionally, it will describe the procedure for identifying new KERs during project implementation. A set of clear measures to ensure sustainability and effective IPR management of STELLA results will be developed by M17 in D6.9, expanding upon this initial plan and providing a concrete roadmap for the duration of the project and beyond.

5.1 STELLA Exploitation strategy and measures

Exploitation strategy is established by M06 as part of the DEC plan, designed to bring STELLA results to all target groups and deliver sustainable outputs that extend beyond the project lifetime. Exploitation plan will effectively:

- Ensure the use, re-use and extensive dissemination of knowledge created during the project.
- Highlight the added value of the project to promote further scientific development.
- Promote sustainable growth (e.g., industry competitiveness).

This implies that exploitation does not only refer to commercialization but includes several non-commercial pathways as well.

- **Scientific:** Scientific outputs such as the STELLA pest and AI models, datasets, methods, prototypes, and any available data generated throughout the course of the project that can be utilised by the scientific community for future research.
- **Commercial:** STELLA PSS, technological foundations, prototypes, and research data are some of the products that can be exploited for commercialisation reasons. These are outputs that can be used to create, expand, or influence markets. Innovative technologies or methods that are developed as part of the project can serve as the first step towards creating a new start-up and entering the market.
- **Policymaking:** Project results may provide policymakers and regulators with evidence-based information that can be useful in the process of forming new policies or changing existing ones. Results and new knowledge emerging from the projects can serve decision-makers while forming strategies in various fields such as health, environment, security, and industry.
- **Training and education:** STELLA E-learning platform and potentially other project results can be used to develop education and training programs for professionals and/or the general public. They can provide skills and knowledge and bring about societal transformation.
- **Other:** Anything that does not fit the above categories.

The exploitation strategy follows a multi-actor approach through 3 cycles:

Cycle 1 - Investigate: Explore partner expectations and ambitions for future development.

STELLA will base its initial exploitation strategy, by mapping all consortium partners' expectations and capabilities. This cycle involves the development of the "KER & IPR validation & identification spreadsheet", which will validate the existing knowledge and information about the project's Key Exploitable Results and their possible IPRs (more information about IPR is provided in chapter 5.3) the partners have already identified.

A dedicated online tool (Annex IV) streamlines the identification and management of Key Exploitation Results (KERs). Partners can easily access and contribute information within the tool, including the potential of each KER, target groups, exploitation methods, and potential intellectual property rights (IPRs). Each KER has its own sheet for individual partner input, allowing for clear collaboration. It will be shared with partners via the project's online folder in order to update their information and add new KERs as the project progresses, ensuring the tool remains current throughout the project lifecycle.

Cycle 2 - Co-create: Continuous mapping and analysis.

STELLA will proceed towards the validation of exploitation scenarios (commercial & non-commercial) and identify the best market fit following the project achievements to fully capture their accumulated value.

The co-create step also includes the identification of possible additional exploitable results that may be developed during the project. Towards this direction, constant communication with partners helps in identifying possible exploitable results, commercial or non-commercial. Certain procedures and steps have been designed and presented in Figure 20:

Figure 21. New KER identification steps

When one or more partners identify a new KER, the partner has to inform the WP6 Leader (FSH) and the Coordinator (AUA) providing a detailed explanation of the exploitability potential of the identified result by making sure it aligns with the project exploitation plan. The partner has to provide all relevant information about this KER using the “KER & IPR validation & identification spreadsheet” (ANNEX VII), covering at least the following aspects:

- Scope of exploitation
- Target groups (to whom)
- Means of exploitation (how)
- Link to possible IPRs

Cycle 3 - Accelerate: Finalise agreements on results' exploitation.

It involves a thorough assessment of the exploitation potential, defining both commercial and non-commercial synergies with potential partners and collaborators. The final version of the Exploitation Plan will be released, detailing the strategies for effectively leveraging project results to maximise their impact and value.

5.2 STELLA KERs

Each exploitable result requires a unique exploitation approach based upon the type of exploitation and whether it can be commercialised. At the time of writing, STELLA has identified the following four key exploitable results (KERs). Tables 29-33 present each of the KERs, the partners that will contribute to their development, a description, the target groups, the scope (commercial, non-commercial) and means of exploitation as well as the unique value proposition. This brief statement clearly explains the benefits, how it solves a particular challenge and how it is different and unique. As the project progresses, each of the KERs will be revisited and analysed in further detail.

5.2.1 KER1: STELLA PSS

Table 30. STELLA KER1

KER 1: STELLA PSS	
Contributing Partners	AUA, ILVO, BOCU, GD, ACTA, PESSL, GSC, AFL, EDEN, IFV, LincolnAgritech
Description	A real time pest and disease monitoring alert and response system, consisting of an early warning tool, a pest detection system and a pest response system.
Target Groups	Agriculture & forestry actors, Policy makers & Regulators, Industry and Technology, Research & Academia
Exploitation Type	Agriculture & forestry actors: Adopt the STELLA PSS for accessing insights for early warning surveillance, detection and mitigation of RNQP & quarantine diseases. Policy makers & Regulators: Access policy recommendations towards accelerating the adoption of digital technologies in agriculture. Industry and Technology: Enable the build of new applications and services. Research & Academia: Exploitation of the scientific breakthroughs under other existing research activities, new research projects and for educational/training purposes.
Scope of exploitation	Commercial (C) & Non-commercial (N)
Unique Value Proposition	A comprehensive system for plant monitoring and disease risk warnings will translate AI models, output into actionable information, towards informed decisions and proactive measures for minimisation of plant health risks.

5.2.2 KER2: E-learning platform

Table 31. STELLA KER2

KER 2: E-learning platform	
Contributing Partners	All Partners
Description	Multimodal platform offering free, online training material towards strengthening the capacities of stakeholders in adopting STELLA's results.
Target Groups	Agriculture & forestry actors, Policy makers & Regulators, Research & Academia, Society
Exploitation Type	Increase capacity, build skills and fill the knowledge gaps that limit stakeholder engagement of harnessing the power of digital technologies to protect plans & the environment.
Scope of exploitation	Commercial (C) & Non-commercial (N)
Unique Value Proposition	Convenient open access to high quality training materials, featuring multidisciplinary modules, specifically designed to support the confident and efficient use of STELLA's solutions.

5.2.3 KER3: Pest models

Table 32. STELLA KER3

KER 3: Pest models	
Contributing Partners	Research Partners
Description	Multimodal platform offering free, online training material towards strengthening the capacities of stakeholders in adopting STELLA's results
Target Groups	Agriculture & forestry actors, Industry and Technology, Academia
Exploitation Type	Implement effective measures for pest control by understanding the epidemiological traits of pests and by making a better quantification of the risks associated with their spread
Scope of exploitation	Non-commercial (N)
Unique Value Proposition	Offer insights for further development of targeted pest control methods and strategies

5.2.4 KER4: AI models

Table 33. STELLA KER4

KER 4: AI models	
Contributing Partners	Research Partners
Description	Development of AI models for end-to-end data collection and estimation for pest detection and prediction integrated in STELLA PSS
Target Groups	Agriculture & forestry actors, Industry and Technology, Academia
Exploitation Type	Exploit the tailor-made AI models for predictions in real time and for pest-specific estimations in the field
Scope of exploitation	Non-commercial (N)
Unique Value Proposition	AI models will support multi-modal input data (images, text, numbers), and are designed to provide macro-predictions and model more complicated phenomena regarding pest presence.

5.3 Sustainability plan and IPR strategy

5.3.1 Sustainability plan

Ensuring the long-term sustainability of the STELLA project's outcomes is crucial for maintaining the impact and benefits of the innovations developed. The sustainability plan outlines the strategies and actions that will be implemented to secure the ongoing relevance, usability, and exploitation of STELLA's solutions beyond the project's lifetime. The key objectives of the sustainability plan are:

- **Institutionalize STELLA Solutions:** Integrate the STELLA platform and its tools into existing agricultural practices, policies, and systems to ensure their continued use and further exploitation.
- **Build Stakeholder Capacity:** Equip stakeholders, including farmers, policymakers, researchers, and industry professionals, with the knowledge and skills necessary to adopt and benefit from STELLA solutions.
- **Foster Strategic Partnerships:** Develop and maintain partnerships with key organisations, institutions, and networks to support the ongoing promotion and use of STELLA innovations.
- **Promote Continuous Improvement:** Establish mechanisms for feedback, evaluation, and iterative improvement of STELLA solutions to adapt to changing needs and emerging challenges.
- **Leverage Funding Opportunities:** Identify and secure additional funding sources, including grants, investments, and public-private partnerships, to support the ongoing development and scaling of STELLA solutions.
- **Enhance Policy Impact:** Engage with policymakers to influence and align with agricultural policies that support sustainable pest management practices and the adoption of digital technologies.

By implementing this sustainability plan, STELLA aims to ensure that the project's innovations continue to deliver value, drive advancements in sustainable agriculture, and support the broader goals of environmental protection and food security.

5.3.2 IPR Strategy

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are the ownership rights for creations of the mind, such as inventions, names, images, or designs and can enable owners to obtain financial benefit from their ideas. An effective IPR strategy is crucial for the STELLA project, ensuring that ownership of project results is clear and facilitates their future exploitation. The STELLA consortium aims to develop a balanced IPR strategy that protects the interests of creators while promoting project outcomes and public benefit.

The STELLA project is expected to generate various forms of intellectual property, potentially including software code, pest and AI models. The project will examine the possibility of protecting these results through mechanisms such as:

- Patent
- Trademark
- Industrial design
- Copyright
- Trade-secret
- Confidentiality
- Geographical indication.

The most suitable form of protection will be determined based on the specific nature of each asset of intellectual property.

FSH, responsible for Task 6.4 (Sustainability & IPR management), will handle Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) through a structured approach across three phases: Proposal, Implementation, and Post-Project. This approach ensures thorough management of IPRs, contributing to the sustainability and impact of the project's outcomes. Deliverable D6.9, due in M17, will expand on this initial plan, providing a concrete roadmap for sustainable and effective IPR management throughout the project and beyond.

1. IPR at Proposal Phase:

The consortium has pre-identified outputs that can be subject to IP/ownership, such as the STELLA PSS. In order to ensure that identical or similar characteristics to an IPR are not already in use, preliminary searches were conducted using open resources (Google Patents, Patent Lens) and tools provided by EUIPO (Espacenet, eSearch plus), EUIPN (TMview), and WIPO (Global Brand Database). These searches confirmed that there are no existing trademarks on the project's acronym, logo, or full title.

2. IPR During the Project:

The Horizon IP Scan service will be utilised by the project's SMEs to assess intangible assets and identify any potential IP issues. Newly generated knowledge and IPR will be recorded, recognized, and assessed using appropriate tools. As part of this procedure, FSH will lead an IPR scan process to identify and manage intellectual property rights generated by the project. This process will include two (2) IPR workshops for all partners, distribution of IPR & Exploitation questionnaires, and potentially one-on-one interviews. The goal is to establish a clear set of IPR measures and a joint exploitation strategy that aligns with the project's overall goals.

Ownership of all identified IP will be clarified. Moreover, the project's published results, including scientific publications and training materials, will be made available without charging IPR. All peer-reviewed and technical publications will be accessible on the STELLA website and in a centralised repository (Open Research Europe) as mandated by the Horizon Europe "Open Science Policy".

3. Post-Project IPR Strategy:

Post-project sustainability hinges on the systematic management of IP risks and the contractual environment. FSH will offer comprehensive services for the entire IPR lifecycle to project partners, including two workshops to address pathways for protecting their results.

6. Conclusion

D6.2 “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan”, has provided an overview of the strategies for communicating, disseminating, and exploiting project results throughout the STELLA project’s lifespan. This initial DEC plan outlines the activities and tools to be implemented during the first phase, focusing on reaching target audiences such as farmers, policymakers, and researchers.

More specifically, the plan establishes clear timelines for a wide range of key activities to be conducted to meet the dissemination, communication, and exploitation targets. All partners will be actively involved in the communication and dissemination of STELLA, aiming to ensure the proper exploitation of the project’s outcomes and maximise the impact.

The second Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan, due in M18, will build upon this foundation. It will evaluate the current plan to identify weaknesses and strengths of the applied activities and tools and establish objectives and concrete actions beyond M18 until the third iteration (M36) that follows with the established and growing ecosystem of STELLA.

Annexes

Annex I: STELLA Templates

Deliverable template

<div style="text-align: center;"> </div>	1	Heading 1	5	1.1	Heading 2	5	1.1.1	Heading 3	5	1.1.1.1	Heading 4	5	1.1.1.1.1	Heading 5	5	1.1.1.1.1.1	Heading 6	5	2	Conclusions	6	3	References	7	4	Annex I: Example Annex title	8	Figure 1	5	Table 1	5	List of Abbreviations and Acronyms		Abbreviation #1	Acronym #1																																										
Grant Agreement No.	101134750																																																																												
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Project Title	Harnessing the Power of Digital Technologies to Protect Plants & the Environment																																																																												
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Minutes template

<div style="text-align: center;">	101134750	Grant Agreement No.		Project Acronym	STELLA	Project Title	Harnessing the Power of Digital Technologies to Protect Plants & the Environment	Type of Action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions	Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-16	Start - End date	January 1 st , 2024 – December 31 st , 2027	Project Website	stella-pss.eu	Work Package	[WPx: Title of the WP]	<div style="text-align: right; margin-bottom: 5px;">Meeting Minutes</div> <p style="margin-bottom: 5px;">Participants</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>No</th> <th>Organisation</th> <th>Name</th> <th>Email</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>2.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>3.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>4.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>5.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>6.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>7.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>8.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>9.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>10.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>11.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>12.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>13.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>14.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>15.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>16.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>17.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>18.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>19.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>20.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p style="text-align: center; margin-top: 20px;">stella-pss.eu</p>	No	Organisation	Name	Email	1.				2.				3.				4.				5.				6.				7.				8.				9.				10.				11.				12.				13.				14.				15.				16.				17.				18.				19.				20.											
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Meeting agenda template

<div style="text-align: center;"> [Meeting Title] Meeting Agenda </div> <p>3. Proposed Agenda</p> <p>1st day of [Meeting Title] meeting: DD/MM/YY</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white;"> <th>Time*</th> <th>Session</th> <th>Presenter</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr style="background-color: #92d050;"><td colspan="3" style="text-align: center;">Tea & Coffee Break</td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr style="background-color: #92d050;"><td colspan="3" style="text-align: center;">Lunch Break</td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr style="background-color: #92d050;"><td colspan="3" style="text-align: center;">Tea & Coffee Break</td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white;"><td colspan="3"> </td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p><small>*Please specify the time zone</small></p> <div style="text-align: right;"> stella-pss.eu </div>	Time*	Session	Presenter				Tea & Coffee Break						Lunch Break						Tea & Coffee Break																												
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Call	HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01																																														
Start – end date Project Duration	01/01/2024 -31/12/2027 48 months																																														
Project Website	stella-pss.eu																																														
Project Coordinator	Agricultural University of Athens (AUA)																																														
Address	Iera Odos 75, 11875, Greece																																														
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Presentation template

Funded by the European Union

Harnessing the Power of Digital Technologies to Protect Plants & the Environment

[Event]
Presentation
Day #

www.stella-pss.eu

[Date]

[Event | Place]

Meeting Agenda Day

<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 45%;"> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <div style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white; padding: 5px; border-radius: 5px; width: 20px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">#</div> <input style="width: 80%; border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;" type="text" value="Click to add text"/> </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <div style="background-color: #76b82a; color: white; padding: 5px; border-radius: 5px; width: 20px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">#</div> <input style="width: 80%; border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;" type="text" value="Click to add text"/> </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <div style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white; padding: 5px; border-radius: 5px; width: 20px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">#</div> <input style="width: 80%; border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;" type="text" value="Click to add text"/> </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <div style="background-color: #76b82a; color: white; padding: 5px; border-radius: 5px; width: 20px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">#</div> <input style="width: 80%; border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;" type="text" value="Click to add text"/> </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white; padding: 5px; border-radius: 5px; width: 20px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">#</div> <input style="width: 80%; border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;" type="text" value="Click to add text"/> </div> </div> </div>	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 45%;"> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <div style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white; padding: 5px; border-radius: 5px; width: 20px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">#</div> <input style="width: 80%; border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;" type="text" value="Click to add text"/> </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <div style="background-color: #76b82a; color: white; padding: 5px; border-radius: 5px; width: 20px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">#</div> <input style="width: 80%; border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;" type="text" value="Click to add text"/> </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <div style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white; padding: 5px; border-radius: 5px; width: 20px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">#</div> <input style="width: 80%; border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;" type="text" value="Click to add text"/> </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <div style="background-color: #76b82a; color: white; padding: 5px; border-radius: 5px; width: 20px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">#</div> <input style="width: 80%; border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;" type="text" value="Click to add text"/> </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white; padding: 5px; border-radius: 5px; width: 20px; text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">#</div> <input style="width: 80%; border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;" type="text" value="Click to add text"/> </div> </div> </div>
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[Date]

[Event | Place] 2

The slide features the STELLA logo in the top left corner, with the tagline "Harnessing the Power of Digital Technologies to Protect Plants & the Environment". A green arrow in the top right corner contains the text "# mins". A large white box in the center contains the text "Click to add title". In the bottom left, there is a small illustration of a plant with the placeholder "[Date]". In the bottom right, there is a placeholder "[Event | Place]" followed by a small number "3". The background is a light blue and white abstract pattern of lines and nodes, resembling a network or data flow. The website address "www.stella-pss.eu" is written vertically on the right side.

Annex II: Communication Material

Logo Variations

Colour pallet and styles

COLOURS	RGB: 043, 088, 119	CMYK: 096, 053, 033, 018 PANTONE 308C WEB: 2B5877	FONTS
	RGB: 077, 132, 157	CMYK: 065, 000, 100, 000 PANTONE 368C WEB: 86B233	
	RGB: 134, 178, 157	CMYK: 084, 029, 027, 008 PANTONE 314C WEB: 4D849D	
Logo font: Neuropol Title font: Zachel_X			

Banner

STELLA
Digital technologies for plant health, early detection, territory surveillance & phytosanitary measures

Harnessing the Power of Digital Technologies to Protect Plants & the Environment

Grape
Farming System Vineyard
Pathogens Grapevine leafroll disease GLRaV-1 & GLRaV-3 (Virus), Candidatus Phytoplasma solani (Bacterium)
Importance RNQP
Location FRANCE

Plane Tree
Farming System Wild Forest
Pathogen Ceratocystis platani (Fungal)
Importance Quarantine
Location GREECE

Potato
Farming System Arable
Pathogen Potato leafroll virus (PLRV) (Virus)
Importance RNQP
Location LITHUANIA

Tomato
Farming System Arable
Pathogen Ralstonia Solanacearum (Bacterium)
Importance Quarantine
Location ITALY

Apples
Farming System Orchard
Pathogen Neofabraea alba (Fungal)
Importance RNQP
Location NEW ZEALAND

Olive Tree
Farming System Orchard
Pathogens Verticillium dahliae (Fungus), Pseudomonas savastanoi (Bacterium)
Importance RNQP
Location GREECE

STELLA PSS
Landscape surveillance
Early warning system
Pest detection system

Partners: GARD, UNIVERSITÀ DI TRIESTE, ILVO, GREEN & DIGITAL, FOODSCALE HUB, AGRI 4.0, HORTIQ, Pessi, Green Supply Chain, Agrifood@LIFE, Eden CUBE, IFV, UNICOLIB, AGRICOLA

social media icons: YouTube, LinkedIn, X, Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp
stella-pss.eu
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Poster

stella-pss.eu

STELLA
 Digital technologies for plant health,
 early detection, territory surveillance
 & phytosanitary measures

Harnessing the Power of Digital Technologies to Protect Plants & the Environment

STELLA
PSS
PLATFORM

Olive Tree

Farming System Orchard
 Pathogens *Verticillium dahliae* (Fungus),
Pseudomonas savastanoi (Bacterium)
 Importance RNQP
 Location GREECE

Grape

Farming System Vineyard
 Pathogens Grapevine leafroll disease *GLRaV-1* & *GLRaV-3* (Virus),
Candidatus Phytoplasma solani (Bacterium)
 Importance RNQP
 Location FRANCE

Apples

Farming System Orchard
 Pathogen *Neofabraea alba* (Fungus)
 Importance RNQP
 Location NEW ZEALAND

Processing Tomato

Farming System Arable
 Pathogen *Ralstonia Solanacearum* (Bacterium)
 Importance Quarantine
 Location ITALY

Potato

Farming System Arable
 Pathogen Potato leafroll virus (PLRV) (Virus)
 Importance RNQP
 Location LITHUANIA

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Brochure

IN A FEW WORDS

STELLA aims to develop a holistic digital system (STELLA PSS) to aid in the early warning and detection of quarantine and regulated plant pathogens, together with a response strategy that uses modern sensing technology and Artificial Intelligence.

STELLA Stakeholders

- Agriculture & Forestry actors
- Policy Makers & Regulators
- Industry & Technology
- Research & Academia
- Society

CHALLENGES

- Regulated Non-Quarantine Pest (RNQP) outbreaks and unintentional introduction of regulated pests
- Lack of monitoring/surveillance systems for quarantine pests and RNQP
- Increased utilization and hazards associated with chemical and hazardous pesticides

COORDINATOR

TEONIKO DIANETIHMIO ARIHNON
AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS

PARTNERS

Funded by the European Union

GET IN TOUCH

Project Coordinator
Prof. Dimitris Tsitsigiannis
Agricultural University of Athens, Greece
email: dimtsi@aua.gr

stella-pss.eu

STELLA

Harnessing the power of **Digital Technologies** to protect plants & the environment

stella-pss.eu

Funded by the European Union

THE STELLA APPROACH

STELLA PSS will be tested over three years on field, farm, and regional levels across 6 Use Case Pilots (UCPs). The project will focus on 8 different quarantine and regulated non-quarantine pest (RNQP) diseases, expanding across 4 European countries with different climate and geological characteristics and New Zealand.

THE STELLA CONCEPT

- STELLA Pest Surveillance System (PSS)**
3 Subsystems (Early warning, Pest detection, Pest response) | Fusion of AI models and digital technologies
- STELLA PSS Platform**
Host STELLA PSS, facilitating data sharing and semantic interoperability through data standardisation and APIs
- Use Case Pilots (UCPs)**
Test STELLA PSS in orchards, vineyards, arable farms and forests
- Capacity Building Activities**
Educate stakeholders to effectively use the STELLA PSS
- Networks and Synergies**
Links and synergies with projects, initiatives, organizations and networks
- Policy**
Policy Recommendations, Policy Roadmap

STELLA USE CASE PILOTS

 Olive Tree Farming System: Orchard Pathogens: <i>Verticillium dahliae</i> (fungus), <i>Pseudomonas savastanoi</i> (bacterium) Importance: RNQP Location: Greece	 Grape Farming System: Vineyard Pathogens: Grapevine leafroll disease <i>GLRaV-1</i> & <i>GLRaV-3</i> (virus), <i>Candidatus Phytoplasma solani</i> (bacterium) Importance: RNQP Location: France	 Plane Tree Farming System: Wild Forest Pathogens: <i>Ceratocystis platani</i> (fungus) Importance: Quarantine Location: Greece
 Processing Tomato Farming System: Arable Pathogens: <i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i> (bacterium) Importance: Quarantine Location: Italy	 Apples Farming System: Orchard Pathogens: <i>Neofabraea alba</i> (fungus) Importance: RNQP Location: New Zealand	 Potato Farming System: Arable Pathogens: Potato leafroll virus (PLRV) (virus) Importance: RNQP Location: Lithuania

• RNQP = Regulated non-quarantine pests

KEY OBJECTIVES

- Develop a holistic digital system to aid in the early warning and detection of pests together with a response strategy by using modern sensing technology and Artificial Intelligence.
- Develop novel plant pest monitoring strategies encompassing and fusing the latest trends and developments in AI, IoT, remote and proximal sensing.
- Test and validate the performance of plant pest monitoring through real life field experiments (UCPs) in commercial farming systems and large, difficult to reach areas.
- Strengthen the capacities of stakeholders in adopting digital technologies for early detection, monitoring, and plant pest prevention.

Proposed merchandise

Annex III: Partners' social media channels

No	Partner	LinkedIn	Facebook	Youtube	Instagram	Twitter
1	AUA	https://www.linkedin.com/in/agricultural-university-of-athens-aua-ofc-3814321aa/	https://www.facebook.com/AgriculturalUniversityofAthens/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCiIRPTax6lrU8I5xY3Fie3g	https://www.instagram.com/agricultural_university_athens/	
2	UCSC	https://www.linkedin.com/school/unicatt/	https://www.facebook.com/unicatt	https://www.youtube.com/user/yunicatt	https://www.instagram.com/unicatt/	https://twitter.com/unicatt
3	EV ILVO	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ilvo/	https://www.facebook.com/ILVOvlaanderen	https://www.youtube.com/@ILVOCOMM	https://www.instagram.com/ilvovlaanderen/	https://twitter.com/ILVOvlaanderen
4	BOKU	https://www.linkedin.com/school/bokuvienna/	https://www.facebook.com/bokuvienna/	https://www.youtube.com/user/bokuwien	https://www.instagram.com/boku.vienna/	https://twitter.com/bokuvienna
5	GREEN & DIGITAL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/green-and-digital/about/	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61556627081607		https://www.instagram.com/green.n.digital/	
6	FSH	https://www.linkedin.com/company/foodscale-hub	https://www.facebook.com/foodscalehub/	https://www.youtube.com/@foodscalehub5618	https://www.instagram.com/foodscalehub/	https://twitter.com/foodscalehub
7	ACTA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/acta---les-instituts-techniques-agricoles/	https://www.facebook.com/ACTA.asso	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqcs8wMgLVzdwYZ6wDTIITA		https://twitter.com/acta_asso
8	HORTA SRL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/horta-s-r-l/	https://www.facebook.com/Horta.srl	https://www.youtube.com/@hortasrl4273	https://www.instagram.com/hortasrl	https://twitter.com/Horta_srl
9	PESSL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/pesslinstruments/	https://www.facebook.com/pesslinstruments/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCai0VFEu-x34fIR_GzbLGfg	https://www.instagram.com/pesslinstruments_pi/	https://twitter.com/metos_austria

No	Partner	LinkedIn	Facebook	Youtube	Instagram	Twitter
10	GSC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/greensupplychain/	https://www.facebook.com/GreenSupplyChainDIH/			https://twitter.com/GreenSupplyCha1
11	AFL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifood-lithuania-dih/	https://www.facebook.com/AgriFood.lt	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXuZLiM7S6CeNPUNLmnX0wQ		https://twitter.com/AgriFoodDIH_LTU
12	EDEN CORE	https://www.linkedin.com/company/edenlib/	https://www.facebook.com/EdenLibraryAI/	https://www.youtube.com/@edenlibrary	https://www.instagram.com/edenlibraryai/	
13	IFV	https://www.linkedin.com/company/institut-fran-ais-de-la-vigne-et-du-vin-ifv-/	https://www.facebook.com/VigneVinFrance	https://www.youtube.com/user/VignevinFrance	https://www.instagram.com/vignevinfrance	https://twitter.com/vignevinfrance
14	Lincoln Agritech	https://www.linkedin.com/company/lincoln-agritech-limited/	https://www.facebook.com/LincolnAgritech	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCchc2JG3ITc62d01Ya4LEFg		https://twitter.com/LincolnAgritech

Annex IV: D&C KPIs explanation

KPI	Explanation
D1 - Scientific Publications	
D1.1 - Peer reviewed open access journal publications	Scholarly papers that have undergone evaluation by field experts. These research papers should be open access.
D1.2 - Scientific conference publications	Conference contributions not necessarily in peer reviewed journals that can fall within other scientific, policy and/or industry platforms.
D2 - Technical Publications	
D2.1 - Technical journals and national magazine publications	Publication of technical briefs in renowned national magazines that specialise in the relevant project fields.
D2.2 - Datasets via OpenAIRE	Image & numeric/ tabular datasets about pest/disease occurrence, site specifications and management shared via OpenAIRE platform.
D3 - Capacity Building	
D3.1 - Capacity building workshops	Workshops refer to interactive sessions designed to provide participants with practical skills, knowledge, and experiences. Workshops will take place within the UCPs (1 per year) in order to increase digital technologies deployment and support key factors (e.g. data, training needs) needed for adopting these technologies.
D3.2 - Number of participating stakeholders	Stakeholders participating the capacity building workshops
D3.3 - E-learning platform with 4 modules	Multimodal platform offering free, online training material towards strengthening the capacities of stakeholders in adopting STELLA's results.
D3.4 - E-learning platform hours of training material	Asynchronous learning material for targeted stakeholders combining visual elements, images, figures and text.

D4 - Policy contribution	
D4.1 - Policy Toolbox	Aimed at policymakers operating at different levels, and covering the importance of effective plant-health management, embracing new technologies in territory surveillance, establishing diagnostic networks, and the use of digital technologies in supporting plant health policies.
D4.2 - Toolbox policy recommendations/briefs supporting plant health policies	To achieve high-scale and long-lasting impact, a toolbox, including policy recommendations and practice abstracts, will be developed towards the empowerment of EU's and Associated Countries' policies on safeguarding plants' health, as well as on the promotion of the digitalization of agriculture.
D4.3 - Practice abstracts reporting technological innovations	Practice abstracts aimed at policymakers operating at different levels.
D4.4 - Guide for policy design	Policy roadmap to assist policy makers adopting digital technologies to support plant health policies and ensure that policy interventions are based on sound research .
D4.5 - Workshop for the STELLA policy network	A workshop for the STELLA policy network and beyond will be organised in Brussels, bringing policy makers together to discuss and learn about the policy recommendations.
D5 - Ecosystem Building	
D5.1 - Participation in conferences	Representation of STELLA at various events: poster or speaker at a conference, presentation, brochure distribution, banner or booth at fairs/expos, panellist or discussion participant in forum.
D5.2 - Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	Engage in collaborative endeavours with EU initiatives/projects to leverage collective expertise, share best practices, and maximise the impact of efforts in the field of the relevant fields.

C1 - Branding & material	
C1.1 - Visual identity & moto	FSH as WP6 lead is responsible for creating the project's visual identity, including the brand book with the project's fonts, colours, logo variations and motto.
C1.2 - Banners	FSH will design the project's banners. Validation may be requested. Partner's may also request specific material to be included.
C1.3 - Brochures	FSH will design the project's brochures and posters. Validation may be requested. Partner's may also request specific material to be included.
C1.4 - Printing & distribution of promotional materials	All partners are expected to print & distribute the brochures at live events and online.
C2 - Website	
C2.1 - Website unique visitors	Unique visitors accessed the STELLA website
C2.2 - Blog posts	Blog posts refer to short (600-200+ word) articles, guides, project updates published on the STELLA website's newsroom. Topics will include features on results updates, partner activities, as well as feature specific topics relevant to the project. FSH will format the posts and upload them to the website. Partners will be expected to draft blog posts relevant to their expertise, organisation and/or specific project work.
C2.3 - Bounce Rate	The percentage of visitors to the Stella website who will navigate away from the site after viewing only one page.
C3 - Social Platforms	
C3.1 - Social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, SlideShare, Instagram)	FSH will create accounts on all the major Social media channels in order to promote Stella.
C3.2 - Total audience	Followers, subscribers and audience engaged to Stella social media accounts .

(continued on next page)

C3 - Social Platforms (continued)	
C3.3 - Social media posts	FSH will post through the STELLA social media channels. All partners are expected to post about the project on their organisation's social media channels and tag Stella.
C3.4 - Total interactions	Number of interactions with STELLA's social media posts.
C3.5 - Hashtags	FSH will create 5 project hashtags that are expected to be used for all STELLA posts.
C4 - Interactive e-newsletter	
C4.1 - E-newsletter subscriptions	FSH will create and distribute the bi-annual e-newsletter. Partners may provide input they would like to be included and are expected to subscribe and share within their organisation's and networks.
C5 - Multimedia	
C5.1 - Press releases	Press releases refer to short descriptions of the project/its key activities and/or key results to be shared with media outlets. Partners are expected to contribute to press release content and to share with local/regional/national/international media outlets.
C5.2 - Press release translations	Designated partners are expected to translate the press release. Translations will be made available to all partners to share with local media outlets .
C5.3 - Videos from the UCPs	Videos to provide a self-explanatory and appealing presentation of each UCP and the project, leveraging available distribution channels of promotion.
C5.4 - Short video/animations	Multimedia material for social media outreach presenting the project vision, impact, results etc.
C5.5 - TV/radio interviews	TV/radio interviews with local/regional/national media, providing reference or discussion about the project and/or its results.

Annex V: Event planning template

1. Event Planning						
#	Name & type of event	Event link (if applicable)	Date & location	Scale	Target groups	Potential STELLA involvement
2. Synergy & Liaison mapping						
#	Type of initiative	Full name	Website	Initiative leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities
3. Publication Planning						
#	Type of publication	Publication website	Estimated submission date			

Annex VI: D&C reporting & monitoring templates

| Reporting Month |
|---|-----------------------------|---|---|---------------------|------|--|---|-----------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------|---|
| | | | | | | <input type="checkbox"/> | | | <input type="checkbox"/> | | |
| | | | | | | <input type="checkbox"/> | | | <input type="checkbox"/> | | |
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| | | | | | | <input type="checkbox"/> | | | <input type="checkbox"/> | | |

Communication KPIs	Overall					1st Reporting Period				Overall Progress per Partner					
	Target	Status	Progress			Target	Status	Progress		1. AUA		2. UCSC			
										Target	Progress	Target	Progress		
C1.1 - Visual identity & motto	1	1	100%		✓	1	1	100%	✓		-	✓		-	✓
C1.2 - Banners	8	1	13%		⌚	1	1	100%	✓		-	✓		-	✓
C1.3 - Brochures	8	0	0%		✗	1	0	0%	✗		-	✓		-	✓
C1.4 - Printing & distribution of promotional materials	2001	0	0%		✗	300	0	0%	✗	150	0%	✗	150	0%	✗
C2.1 - Website unique visitors	15001	0	0%		✗	3000	0	0%	✗		-	✓		-	✓
C2.2 - Blog posts	51	2	4%		⌚	15	2	13%	⌚	6	0%	✗	1	0%	✗
C2.3 - Bounce Rate	49	0	0%		✗	49	0	0%	✗		-	✓		-	✓

Annex VII: STELLA KER & IPR validation & identification spreadsheet

Partner	Identified Background Confirmation (This is the description in the Consortium Agreement for your organisation)	Partner's Confirmation	Link Background with STELLA KERs					
			1: STELLA PSS	2: E-learning platform	3: Pest models	4: AI models	5: (Add new KER)	6: (Add new KER)
1. AUA	No data, know-how or information of the partner is needed by another Party for implementation of the Project or Exploitation of that other Party's Results.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. UCSC	Modelling knowledge for pest and diseases, several models developed for non-regulated pests on grape, olive and tomato.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. EV ILVO	No data, know-how or information of the partner is needed by another Party for implementation of the Project or Exploitation of that other Party's Results.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. BOKU	COALA API and data for precision farming	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Earth Observation Data Centre (EODC)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Partner (By whom)	II. RESULT DETAILS													
	Result type			Potential				Audience or target group (To whom)			Exploitation			
				Does the result have a high potential?							Means of exploitation* (Please indicate means of exploitation, where relevant)		Market maturity*	
	Main	Secondary (if applicable)	Notes	Main	Secondary (if applicable)	Description of high potential (max. 200 characters)	Main	Secondary (if applicable)	Notes	Main	Secondary (if applicable)	Notes	State of the market targeted by this result	
1. AUA														
2. UCSC														
3. EV ILVO														
4. BOKU														